

Baltic MUPPETS

DELIVERABLE 2.7

Report on optimized harvest
system

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1. BACKGROUND AND AIM OF THE TASK

Until today, mussel farming on the Swedish east coast has only been conducted on a small pilot/prototype scale and has mostly relied on labor-intensive and costly harvesting methods and logistics solutions. Although this way of working has been effective enough to drive development forward, it does not provide the conditions for a financially sustainable business. In Ecopelag, to make mussel farming more cost-effective, we have designed a new harvester and harvesting system through evaluation, testing and adaptation of different sub-components.

The focus of this harvesting method has been on the integration and adaptation of already existing technologies and solutions in both mussel and fishing industries. The test work and adaptations in the field have primarily been carried out by Ecopelag, while the design of components has also included external expertise, such as designers and equipment manufacturers. The development of the harvester is a result of several projects, in addition to Baltic MUPPETS, also the EU projects Baltic Blue Growth¹ and Life IP Rich waters².

2. HARVEST EQUIPMENT

2.1 Choice of harvest method

The starting point for Ecopelag's harvesting method has been the technology already used in the Netherlands, amongst other places, for harvesting of long-line systems. A system that can harvest large volumes in a short amount of time significantly lowers production costs and reduces the time that the harvested mussel needs to be stored before processing. Ecopelag has had discussions with several European machine manufacturers to investigate different alternatives. In Sweden, Ecopelag got in touch with Vattenbrukscentrum Ost, the initiator of mussel farming in the Sankt Anna archipelago in East Sweden Region, to integrate their equipment into Ecopelag's operations.

This equipment initially comes from the company Bakker (www.wbakker.com) and was mounted on a wooden platform (approx. 5x10 meters) designed within the Baltic Blue Growth project. A hydraulic system had also been installed, to drive the crane and harvesting equipment. The harvesting equipment consists of a conveyor belt transporting substrate rope through a scraper with rubber panels. The scraper separates mussels from the substrate, and

¹ Baltic Blue Growth #R031 on <https://interreg-baltic.eu/projects>

²LifeIP Rich waters, LIFE15 IPE/SE/000015 on <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/search>

after that the mussels are transported into a big bag or box. Normally, for mussel farms in more saline areas, the now empty substrate ropes would then be transported with the help of several drive wheels to bags or boxes for storage on land, until the next settling period for mussels (typically in springtime). This is a common practice to avoid biofouling organisms to take over the empty space and hinder a new mussel settling. In the low saline Baltic proper, however, biofouling is scarce. Because of this, the machinery had been modified within Baltic Blue Growth to re-set the substrate ropes back into the sea immediately after harvest (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Left: Sketch of a long-line mussel farm. Substrate ropes with growing mussels, which are scraped off at harvest, and hang down in loops from a headline. Right: Harvesting at the Sankt Anna mussel farm with the wooden raft and harvesting equipment.

2.2 Optimization of the harvest system

Ecopelag's new harvester is based on an aluminium barge that was acquired from the project Life IP Rich waters. In Baltic MUPPETS, this barge has been modified with new superstructures. The new design has made it possible for Ecopelag to decrease the manpower needed for harvest from 3 to 2 persons, compared to the old system.

The aluminum barge was equipped with three separate towers, each with a set of capstan and hydraulic drive wheels (starwheels). Capstans (winches) are used to catch the headline and lift it over the starwheels. The starwheels are used to pull the harvester forward along the headline during harvest. This means that the motor can be shut off, and no boat-driver is needed. Apart from saving one personnel, this also gives the harvester a more even pace of operation. When the new harvester was ready, the Bakker harvest system from Baltic Blue Growth (Figure 2) was moved from the original platform and mounted on to this new barge. Finally, it was equipped with a new washing stage in the form of a drum washer, originally a shrimp-washer.

The figures 2-7 below show some of the original blueprints drawn by Ecopelag for construction:

Figure 2. Placement, design, and montage of three towers on the barge, with capstans and star wheels.

Figure 3. Determination of the best hold and angle of the starwheels.

Figure 4. Step 3. Placement and design of capstans.

Figure 5. Step 4. Final design of the new harvest barge

Figure 6. Launching of the new harvester in Nynäshamns harbour, June 2023.

Figure 7. Sorting and washing. In addition to the harvesting equipment itself, the barge has also been supplemented with a washing step in the form of a drum washer, originally a shrimp-washer.

2.2.2 Sorting and washing

Clean, separated and sorted mussels provide significantly better conditions for continued processing, but also extend the shelf life of the mussels, as most algae and dead mussels are sorted out, which would otherwise accelerate decomposition. In addition to rinsing away debris, the modified shrimp-washer separates the mussels from each other and sorts out the smallest mussels. The new washer has been placed so that the bigger mussels can pass through the washing drum before they go down into the big bag, while small mussels are collected at the side.

3. HARVEST OPERATION

3.1 Description of the harvest method

Through the development work and improvements that have been implemented, the workforce has been reduced from three to two people. However, to manage the tasks required for a harvest in a safe and efficient manner, a crew of two people is required (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The new harvester testing the newly attached starwheels. Photo: Johan Hammar

The following steps are included in the harvesting process (Figure 9):

1. Catch the headline with a grapnel, winch it up and put it on the starwheels.
2. Move the pram along the starwheels to reach the substrate loops.
3. Grab the first loop and cut off the small rope attaching the end of the substrate rope to the headline.
4. Pull the rope-end through the scraper with help of the conveyer.
5. Continue to feed the whole substrate rope through the scraper, by cutting it off loop by loop from the headline as the starwheels continue to pull the harvester forward.
6. In parallel with the loops being cut, re-attached the clean substrate that comes out at the other end of the scraper back to the headline, and put the substrate rope back into the sea in new loops.
7. The mussels are transported on the conveyer to pass through the washer/size sorter and end up in different big bags depending on the size.
8. When a big bag is full, it is moved by crane and a new big bag is put in place
9. When all the mussels from one long-line unit are harvested, the headline is lifted off using the capstan system and the pram is moved to the next unit.

Figure 9. Left: The barge is pulled along the headline to the substrates. Right: The first end of the substrate rope is cut loose from the headline and thread through the scraper with a puller.

3.2 Conclusions

Under good conditions and good mussel growth, about 1 ton of mussels can be harvested per hour (Figure 10). As technology is still under development, there are some steps left before this pace can be maintained for a full workday. The reason is mainly that a lot of time is spent correcting, solving, and adapting various settings and work steps. A lot of manual work still needs to be done to ensure an efficient harvest. However, progress is constantly made towards the optimal processing steps and handling, as well as further progress regarding the technical parts.

As mentioned before, an advantage in the low saline Baltic proper is that mussels have few competitors, so there is no need to take the substrates back to shore until the next growth season to limit biofouling. Instead, they can be put back in the sea immediately.

Figure 10. Under good circumstances, the new harvester can take 1 ton per hour.